

Motivational Analysis Behind Cyber Criminal Behaviour in Nigeria

Edafe Ulo ✉

*Department of Criminology and Security Studies,
Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria*

Mathias Oghenetejiri Obire Ph.D ✉

*Department of Sociology and Social Studies,
Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria*

Collins Emudiaga Akpumuvie ✉

*Department of Sociology and Social Studies,
Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria*

Helen Eloho Ogbeide ✉

*Department of Sociology and Social Studies,
Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria*

Abstract

The invention of the cyberspace showcased in the use of internet, a necessary tool that has come to stay, defining how people interact and communicate on daily basis, defiling the phenomenon of time and space, thereby making the world a global community. The internet can be said to be a two edged sword that is advantageous and can be destructive depending on the application and user motivations. It's on this note that the work analyzes the motivations behind cybercriminal behaviour in Nigeria, Identifying 'anonymity in cyberspace, thrill-seeking, financial gain, revenge seeking, addiction, law enforcement and weak cyber security' as the key motivations behinds cybercriminal behaviours. 'Routine Activity Theory' was used to analyze the work, anchoring it on the premise of 'motivated offender'. The study concluded with recommendations that government and stakeholders in the cyberspace industries, need to prioritize investment in 'law enforcement and weak cyber security' overhauling the security architecture in charge of prosecutions and investigation of cybercrime activities/offenses, which guarantee protection of confidential data and reduce the risk of cybercrimes.

Keywords: *internet communication, user motivation, anonymity, cyberspace, data protection.*

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Introduction

The rapid growth of the cyberspace through the inventions of the world wide web and internet, specifically showcased with the utilizations of various social media and online applications, has opened up a vast realm of opportunities, but it has also given rise to a new breed of criminals which explore the cyberspace in the disguise of anonymity to perpetual internet related crime known as cybercrime. These internet and social media forms what constitutes digital tool, cyber criminals employs to engage in hacking, identity theft, ransom ware attacks and online frauds, exploiting other internet users that fall prey to them. If cybercrime is to be combated or at least curtailed effectively, it becomes necessary for one to understand the motivation that forms the psychological factors that propels the cybercriminals. Morgan (2017) averred, the important role the internet plays can't be overemphasized as it accounts to

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general applications and development in all works of life, on a contrary, it has also constituted a serious threat to humanity, institutions and the world in general with grievous consequences.

Cybercrime has a global record cost of \$8 trillion in the year 2023, up from \$3 trillion in 2015, signifying the largest transfer of economic wealth in history and more profitable than the worldwide trade in all major illegal narcotics combined. Cybercrimes that are financially driven usually requires a high degree of organization and specialization (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2013).

Jegede, Oyesomi, and Olorunyomi, (2016) in their analysis reported that cybercrime has become a serious social problem to the world at large. The internet has become veritable tools that individual and organization key to in their daily lives for ease of doing business. The attachment to the cyberspace thus created an opportunity for erring cybercriminal who commit simple cyber fraud to major organised crime that exploit and extort other user, which has constituted a threat to the global economy. In the position of Okeshola and Adeta (2013) Although all crimes both simple and complex requires some forms of skills and expertise but necessary skill needed for the commencement of cybercrimes is minimal, as it commands ease of learnability and understanding. The resource of commencement is small and simple talent. The internet space grants the individual identity concealment which is a veritable component that motivates the beginner to join without fears. The concealing features further make illegality of act itself difficult to prove before a court of constituent jurisdiction (Jegede, Oyesomi, & Olorunyomi, 2016).

Suleman (2016), the concept 'cyberspace crimes' as differentiated from the 'physical space crimes' is the recognition that the former, operates within the use of computer application tools to commit crimes that are traditionally committed in the physical space (age old crimes); a good examples; using cyberspace for trafficking. While the latter, recognizes that the age old long crimes that operates within the human terrestrial bodies (Ogwezzy, 2012; McGuire & Dowling, 2013). It was also proven that 43.6% African users of internet are actually Nigerian, hence, the high increase in the rate of cybercrime in Nigeria (Hassan, 2021).

Presently, cybercrimes are performed by people of all ages ranging from young to old, but in most instances the young. Wang and Lewis (2021) reported that Nigeria is also an example of a country where basic industries have declined, with the economy dependent on oil as the basic export. Cross (2018) views cybercrime and by extension, fraud as a reflection of a symptom of the general larger social problems of the Nigeria nation. Furthermore, maintaining that this act has not only having a negative impact on the lives of Nigerians both home and abroad but gradually snowballed into producing a diminishing economic problem, especially in the areas of ease of doing business. In Ulo, (2022 and 2023) he reported that Juvenile and youths with moral deficit now take solace in anonymity of the cyberspace to be highly ingrained in cybercrime for economic and showmanship marathon to parade their illegal wealth. This paper tends to analyze 'Motivational Analysis Behinds Cyber Criminal Behaviour in Nigeria' with focus on; anonymity, thrill seeking, revenge and financial gain in Nigeria.

The Concept of Cybercrime

The writers defined 'cybercrime' as an instigated or intentionally criminal minded initiated crime done with the aids of the computer and its associated applications or tools for personal interest or values. Establishing a definition that will accommodate a much wider spectrum, capturing the duality of the concept, Ogwezzy (2012) maintained, 'cybercrime' are actions or crimes carried out through or with the aid of a computer and its application tools. Contrasting, to 'computer crime' these are intention and unintentional crimes against computer and its application tools". Cybercrime is a new trend that is gradually growing as the internet continues to penetrate every sector of our society and no one can predict its future. The crime usually requires a hectic task to trace. Generally, cybercrime may be divided into one of two types of categories: 1. Crimes that affects computer networks and devices directly. Examples are malicious code, computing viruses, malware etc. 2. Crimes aided by computer gargets/applications, targets are computer networks or device. Examples include Cyber Stalking, Fraud and identity theft, phishing scams and information warfare (Omodunbi, Odiase, Olaniyan & Esan, 2016).

Routine Activity Theory and CyberCrime

Cohen and Felson 'Routine Activity Theory' is a tested theoretical assumption established in the years 1979. The theory has been utilised by many criminologists, sociologists, psychologists and beyond. The theory houses the assumptions, maintaining that for any crime to take place, three of the following premises identified below must be intersectly present.

- An available favorable target of interest; a person or an object that is of interest and values must be available to the offender to prey on.
- The absence of appropriate guardian necessary to prevent a crime; This refers to removing opportunities that are naturally and artificially instigators of crimes and further putting in place deterrent consequences like; laws and suitable punishments, police patrols, guards, neighborhood watch, technological systems, structural designs and even dogs etc.
- The present of a motivated offender; motivated offender is very key if crime must take place, this is because for every crime to take place the intent of the criminal must be taken recognized which is mensrea (the criminal mind/motivations).

The theorist argued that cumulative of the three identified axioms constitutes the production of crime but the motivation is key. This is why the theory thus became appropriate to explaining 'Psychological Motivation on Cyber Criminal Behaviour in Nigeria' It's important to know that opportunity is a veritable tool that the criminal first take cognizance of, as opportunity is an established variable believed by criminologist as the root cause of crime. The successful commission of cybercrime greatly increases as the cybercriminal defies the limitations of 'time and locations'. The cyber space gives the motivated offender greater opportunity for commission of cybercrimes as the space offers them guarantee features of identity concealment. The assumptions of RAT was later tested in 2009 in the works of Bossler and Holt, the outcome confirmed replicability especially when paired with variables like; "On-line Activities, Guardianship, and Malware Infection.

Conceptual Frame

Motivations behind Cybercrime

The writers describe 'motivation' as a force that propels us to act or omit to act. Motivation is the reason for the behaviour of an individual. For Guay et al. (2010) described the concept as follows; "if one is moved to do or not to do something"; the force behind that move is 'motivation'. This definition comes from the basis that human actions are driven by underlying behaviour. It is a combination of closely related interests, values, social constructions and systems of inter-subjective belief. Motivation has three implications for cybercrime. Firstly, it influences the nature and pattern of the crime. Motives are the key push factors to romance scam, phishing, inheritance scam, fake news, cyberespionage, and pharming. Making money is a core motive and leading cause of cybercrime (Bernik, 2014; Olowu, 2009). It contributes to crimes like sextortion, where people are bullied and threatened for monetary benefit. Kopecky (2017) states, that child online blackmail is driven by ulterior motive of the offender. Motivation determines the expected outcome and the type of cybercrime to commit.

Secondly, motivation influences the targets of crime. Cybercriminals have used their motive to select their targets. The situation of victims remains fundamental to the crime. Findings from researching 106 countries by Hui et al. (2017) show that DDoS attacks in the banking, ICT and telecommunication sector are propelled by financial motivation. For example, the motivation to retrieve valuable trade secrets or intellectual properties can influence cyber espionage by competing companies. Thirdly, motivation influences pattern of the cybercrime. As Kaur (2013) explained, motivation drives the action of humans and determines the system to apply. All criminal behaviour hinges on the reasons and justifications for the cybercriminal act. A cybercriminal selects the process of crimes based on such grounds (McGuire & Dowling, 2013). For example, a cybercriminal driven by political considerations will use high technology

tools to attack government networks such as websites, services, and offices. The influence of motivation on Cybercrime is fundamental in its perpetration. Based on these factors, it is essential to consider the various motives for engaging in cybercrime. Putting every category of cybercriminals into a single homogenous level of motivation is never appropriate (Holt, Freilich & Chermak, 2017). Andersen (2012) noted that cybercrimes have numerous players that have vastly different kinds of motivation. In this research, five applicable incentives have been selected based on their contextual relevance.

Psychosocial motivation is also evident within the cybercrime context. Cybercriminals can be motivated by the need to exercise both emotional and mental punishment on victims. Ibrahim (2016b) stated that crimes such as cyber rape, cyber harassment, and cyber stalking are motivated by the desire to inflict psychological distress. Based on the binary classification of motivation, non-financial motivations are psychosocial because they do not rely on monetary gain. Berson (2003) noted that benefits retrieved from the sexual exploitation of internet users could be psychosocial. Hence, the perpetrator is motivated by threatening the mental and emotional health of the victim. The benefits derived from this are psychological, which make it difficult to detect or measure. Crimes that are driven by non-financial motivation consist of intense emotional sensations and elements (Ibrahim, 2016a). The psychological satisfaction of making the victim suffer directly fuels the motivation of perpetrators (Li, 2017). It is a highly emotional crime, and the perpetration often arises from a revenge motive. It is due to mental illness or child abuse experienced by the cybercriminal.

The effect on victims is highly significant because it directly victimises their personality, emotions, psychology, health, and relationships. Wolak et al. (2008) stated that significant emotional sensations resulted in the use of violence and fatalities. For example, Gabrielle Green committed suicide because of criminal behaviour experienced online from those who derive psychosocial pleasure from their acts (Lynch, 2018). This motivation could escalate and go beyond the intended intensity of the perpetrators. However, this motivation is not new to cybercrime either. It exist offline long before the advent of the internet as cybercriminals exploit human weaknesses. The online psychology based crime exhibited patterns that are similar to what obtainable offline. It is a potent reason that made the internet a dangerous place for psychologically and emotionally unstable users.

Analysis of Motivation Behind Cyber Criminal Behaviour

Below are some of the writers identified motivations that propel cyber-criminal behaviours among Nigerians.

Anonymity in Cyberspace

The anonymity provided by social media platforms makes it easier for one to confidently get involved in cyber criminalities, ranging from, hacking, online scams, and banks scams (Oyebade & Onyekwena, 2020). By concealing their true identities, these individuals can perpetrate these crimes with reduced fear of being identified or apprehended. Anonymity triggers the cybercriminal to engage in online harassment and bullying. They may create anonymous accounts to target their peers or others with hurtful comments, threats, or offensive content, leading to emotional distress and potentially criminal charges (Safko & Brake, 2009).

Anonymity can facilitate the formation of illicit peer networks, where young people connect with like-minded individuals for cybercriminal activities. These networks can involve drug trafficking, gang recruitment, or the planning of illegal activities with reduced risk of exposure. Anonymity can also contribute to the spread of false information and disinformation. This could include rumors or fake news that incites violence or unrest, leading to criminal acts or disturbances. Anonymity can play a role in the radicalization of youths. Ulo (2023), describes

‘Anonymity’; as the privacy immunity that covers the internet user’s true identity as he engages in cyberspace, which enhances status transition. Anonymity is an important factor, if not the root cause, of internet fraud in Nigeria.

Cybercriminal Behaviour in Cyberspace

The various criminal behaviour internet fraudster exhibits in cyberspace are extensively discussed in line with the sub-headings below.

Cyberspace Anonymity Motivations

The position of anonymity in cyberspace is a resounding one in the literature of cybercriminology, where individuals capitalise on the immunity of the internet to perpetuate their actions. Ulo (2023) recorded several cases where pastors, business men, law enforcement officials, lecturers, and students transits the physical space statuses to something different within the confines of the internet space due to the assurance the space guarantees the internet user. Ulo, (2023) reported a 33 years old male, who gave a lucid explanation as captured below:

“The anonymity of cyber space, have made me not be apprehended by law enforcement agent, I will not say much, Frobe, never knew Abass Ramoni popularly known as Hushpuppi and Gucci Lord, was involved in internet fraud, until he was arrested. In as much you play low and never become too greedy, nobody can arrest you” (IDI/Male/ 31 years).

Further buttress the anonymity syndrome, was well captured in the newspaper report below;

PM News Nigeria, 17th March, 2022 Reported that:

It was recorded that, Kelechi Vitalis Anozie, a renowned pastor in Nigeria, whom name is on the United States, Federal Bureau of Investigation, FBI wanted list has been arrested by operatives of EFFC. The Commission asserted that Anozie and four other suspects: Valentine Iro, Ekene Ekechukwu (alias Ogedi Power), Bright Azubuike (alias Bright Bauer Azubuike) and Ifeanyi Junior were wanted for allegedly defrauding one F.F of the sum of \$135,800 US Dollars and another \$47,000’ (Ulo, 2023).

This is the kind of immunity, under the umbrella of anonymity in cyberspace that internet fraudsters enjoy in our country. Unfortunately, this has encouraged many more to join, as those who have made it or hit it through scams sort of serve as role models in a recessed economy and a society of declining moral latitude, not minding or, rather, realising the bleak future their boom portends.

The temptation to get involved in cybercrime might be attributed the level anonymity and unlimited defilement of distance to attract victims. Law enforcement agencies find it difficult to track/fight cybercriminal especially with the account of identity cloning and boundary less jurisdictions, orchestrated by anonymity of the cyber space. The limitation to venture into the cybercrime world as a beginner is relatively minimal. The access to right information’s from experts and necessary tools grants the individuals, even the neophyte with limited skill can engage in cybercrime activities. Also, financially orchestrated gains paired with promises of identity concealment are factors (Schamelleger & Volk, 2018; Brown, Geis, & Esbensen, 2010).

Thrill-Seeking Motivations

Reynolds (2024) opinioned that thrill-Seeking tactics play a pivotal role in many cybercrimes, leveraging psychological manipulation to deceive individuals and organizations into unwittingly revealing confidential information, performing actions that compromise security, or granting unauthorized access to systems and data. Phishing is one of the most common social engineering tactics employed by cybercriminals. It involves sending fraudulent emails, messages, or websites that appear legitimate to trick recipients into revealing sensitive information such as login credentials, financial data, or personal details. Another one is piggybacking, which involves gaining unauthorized physical access to restricted areas or systems by exploiting trust or social norms. For certain individuals, the exhilarating thrill of outsmarting sophisticated security systems and gaining notoriety within clandestine online communities serves as a powerful motivation for engaging in cybercrimes. The primary driving force behind these illicit activities is not merely financial gain, but rather the adrenaline rush of navigating through digital defenses and the insatiable desire for recognition among peers in the shadowy realms of the internet. Some cybercriminals

are driven not only by personal gain or thrill-seeking but also by ideological or political motives, leveraging their digital prowess to advance specific agendas (Sharma, 2023).

Notably, it delves into specific instances such as the (2021 NodeIPC attack), where a library owner created malicious software targeting computers in Russia and Belarus as a form of digital protest. Moreover, it illuminates the intricate interplay between geopolitical tensions and the landscape of cybercrimes, highlighting how international conflicts and rivalries can exacerbate online threats and shape the strategies of malicious actors (Hendery, 2023). The ability for cyber criminals to scout for vulnerable prey, scrutinize and exploit them isn't possible except with one that possesses high technicalities and skills. The thrill to breach a computer system or obtain sensitive information, successfully lead to a compulsive desire for subsequent illegal activities. The ability of technical skills possessed by them instigates thrill to outsmart vulnerable victims in or through the computer system.

Financial Gain Motivations

Ulo and Jike (2022), Ulo, (2022) maintained that juveniles and youths get involved in internet fraud as a result of achieving financial gain. Financial Gains is one of the most popular variables, generally agreed in cybercrime studies. This motivation remains as old as the internet. Fraud and financial reward are the reasons for crimes such as identity theft, phishing and others. Fraud over the internet is of significant concern because of the monetary gains (Lavorgna & Sergi, 2016). McGuire and Dowling (2013) note that crimes are often aimed mostly at financial income or personal profit. For example, malware deployments for accessing bank accounts are used to withdraw money illegally. "Fraud is the Daughter of Greed" The quotation attributed to John Grant has characterised the primary public perception of cybercriminals. Scholars argue that greed provides financial motivation for these crimes (Agwu et al., 2018; Broadhurst et al., 2014). Recidivism by cybercriminals and increasing perpetration by those who have gained value of interest from the act are pushed by greed syndrome. Even when perpetrators have attained economic sufficiency, they continue the crime to satisfy their insatiable desire.

The emphasis on greed can be subjective or based on a moral perception rather than an objective analysis. Some cybercriminals require continuous financial gain from their enterprise because of their environment or location (Mustard, 2010; Nicholson & Higgins, 2017). In developing countries where every citizen is provided with their basic needs such as shelter, power, security, education and healthcare, the flow of financial income through crime may be the reason for recidivism. In some instances, the cybercriminal caters to the needs of members of the local community. Hence, the sense of responsibility and the environment can be a significant driving force that is wrongly perceived as greed.

Revenge Seeking Motivations

(Payback Time; The Colonial Experience)

It is now a common discussion in some segment of Nigeria societies, that the proceed form internet fraud is not evil but harvesting the pains the colonial masters inflicted on our ancestors during slave trade era and colonialism. Most internet fraudster term it revenge time to re-loot the looted items from African soil back to Africa. There is belief in by intending new recruit into hustling kingdom (HK). Revenge is another motivation that is assuming greater importance in the criminological understanding of cybercrime. This motivation manifests in different ways. The first is seeking revenge via child blackmail. Kopecky et al. (2014) discover that online blackmail victims confessed to having been part of the same crime, thereby sustaining the crime cycle. In most cases, victims often turned into offenders. Revenge often stems from the desire of the child to seek revenge based on previous experience or a desire to experience a similar feeling to that experienced as a victim (Kopecky, 2017). Another form of revenge motivation may be linked to economic frustration. Broadhurst et al. (2014) cited an arrested cybercriminal who stated that the loss of jobs created the motive to attack businesses. It is claimed that the most dangerous hackers are unemployed Russian cyber specialists (Karatgozianni, 2010). It could represent the fulfillment of one or more of the needs identified earlier by Maslow (1954).

Addictive Motivations

Cybercrime can be highly addictive for people involved in such activities due to different factors such as the excitement of committing illegal activities, anonymity, easy access to information, computer addiction, and the challenge of equivocating law enforcement. A study by Griffiths et al. (2017) explored the concept of "technological addictions" and found that people who participate in cybercrimes, such as hacking or identity theft, may display addictive behaviors. The study emphasized the potential psychological rewards and reinforcement patterns that can contribute to the addictive nature of cybercrime.

Additionally, the financial gains associated with cybercrime can also make it addictive for people to quit the act. A report by the Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) estimated that cybercrime costs the global economy over \$600 billion annually, making it a profitable industry for cybercriminals. The idea of making easy money can be a powerful motivator for people to continue participating in cybercrime, even as they face the risks of being caught and prosecuted.

Law Enforcement and Weak Cyber Security Motivations

The whole essence of cyber law is to create codified rules that regulate the activities of internet users while exchanging communications in the cyber space. This is to ensure the protection of intellectual property rights, freedom of speech and public access to information in cyber space. Also of importance is 'cyber ethics' the upholding responsible behavior while utilizing the cyber space (Umejiaku & Anyaegbu, 2016). The 'Cyber Crime Act' as promulgated in 2015 was designed to handle, tackle and regulate cyber-criminal offenses. The above identified regulations as established are marred with various challenges of implementations.

The weak and incapables nature of the Nigeria Law enforcement agencies is an important veritable tool that must be enhanced and empowered, if the motivations to cybercrimes must be curtailed. The criminal justice system in all ramifications is ill equipped, lacking modern innovative technology that can track and monitor activities of cybercriminals. The absence of technological tools and manpower by the Nigeria law enforcement sector in discharging their duties and responsibilities, especially in areas of implementation creates a veritable motivation for individuals to thrive in cyber-criminal activities.

Cyber criminals are also motivated by insufficient or weak cyber security measures in organizations. When companies have weak or outdated security protocols in place, it creates a more attractive target for hackers. This can include outdated software, lack of encryption, ineffective access controls, and poor password management. The lag in the above creates a loophole for cybercriminals to thrive, to affirm, Deepwatch ATI, Annual Threat Report of 2024, maintained that 'Information Stealing Malware Will Continue to Become More Sophisticated, Abuse of Legitimate Internet Services Will Continue, and Rise of Non-Malware-Based Cyber Attacks among others will likely witness increase in 2024. The impact that weak cyber security may have on the overall success and growth of an organization is enormous. 'IBM Security' 2024 report affirmed that the average cost of a data breach in 2024 was \$4.88 USD with an annual increase of 10%, a breach affected over 600 organizations. The weakness of the cyber security architecture may serve as a motivating factor for cyber criminals, especially when they understand that organizations don't properly man or invest meaningful in their cyber security tech.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Studying the motivations behind cybercrimes is a complex evolving field that requires recurrent researches. Understanding the motivational conditions to cybercrime changes overtime as society evolves with regards to social, psychological, economic and technological changes. Some of the motivations identified by in this paper are; anonymity in cyberspace, thrill-seeking, financial gain, revenge seeking, addiction, law enforcement and weak cyber security motivations. Understanding these factors that drive individuals to engage in cybercrime is crucial for developing effective cybercrimes prevention strategies and implementations of cybercrimes law and enforcement. This will help hamper the threat instigated by

cybercriminal that has and will always ravage our society if not well managed. A focus on the identified strategies will address the root causes and motivations behind cybercrimes in society and will enhance safer and more secure digital environment for us all. To conclude, cogent implementation by law enforcement institutions/officials and insufficient cyber security measures remain the utmost priority. Government and other organizations need to prioritize investment in those two sectors to ensure the overhauling of the security agencies in charge of prosecutions and investigation of cybercrime activities/offenses. This will gradually snowball into securing the protection of confidential data and reduce the risk of cybercrimes.

References

- Agwu, E., Okpara, A., Ikpefan, O., & Aigbiremolen, M. O. (2018). Impediments to e-banking services marketing in developing economies: A case study of Nigerian banks. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 228-248. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3420438>
- Andersen, S. H. (2012). Unemployment and crime: Experimental evidence of the causal effects of intensified ALMPs on crime rates among unemployed individuals (No. 38). *Rockwool Foundation Research Unit*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2151275>
- Armin, J., Foti, P., & Cremonini, M. (2015a, August). Zero-day vulnerabilities and cybercrime. In *Availability, Reliability and Security (ARES), 2015 10th International Conference on* (pp. 711-718). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ARES.2015.74>
- Armin, J., Thompson, B., Ariu, D., Giacinto, G., Roli, F., & Kijewski, P. (2015b, August). 2020 cybercrime economic costs: No measure no solution. In *Availability, Reliability and Security (ARES), 2015 10th International Conference on* (pp. 701-710). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ARES.2015.73>
- Bernik, I. (2014). *Cybercrime and cyber warfare*. John Wiley & Sons. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119002611>
- Berson, I. R. (2003). Grooming cybervictims: The psychosocial effects of online exploitation for youth. *Journal of School Violence*, 2(1), 5-18. https://doi.org/10.1300/J202v02n01_02
- Broadhurst, R., Grabosky, P., Alazab, M., Bouhours, B., & Chon, S. (2014). An analysis of the nature of groups engaged in cyber crime. *International Journal of Cyber Criminology*, 8(1), 1-29. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.35357>
- Brown, S. E., Esbensen, F., & Geis, G. (2010). *Criminology: Explaining crime and its context* (Seventh Edition). Mathew Bender & Company, Inc.
- Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS). (2018). The economic impact of cybercrime—No slowing down. Retrieved from <https://www.mcafee.com/enterprise/en-us/assets/reports/rp-economic-impact-cybercrime.pdf>
- Chantler, A. N. (1995). Risk: The profile of the computer hacker (unpublished thesis). *Curtin University, Australia*.
- Cohen, L. E., & Felson, M. (1979). Social change and crime rate trends: A routine activity approach. *American Sociological Review*, 44(1), 588-608. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2094589>
- Cyber Crime Act 2015. <https://www.nfiu.gov.ng/images/Downloads/downloads/cybercrime.pdf>
- Griffiths, M., Van Rooij, A. J., Kardefelt-Winther, D., Starcevic, V., Király, O., Pallesen, S., Müller, K. W., Dreier, M., Carras, M., Prause, N., & King, D. L. (2017). Working towards an international consensus

on criteria for assessing internet gaming disorder: A critical commentary on Petry et al. (2014). *Addiction*, 112(10), 2126-2130. <https://doi.org/10.1111/add.13719>

Guay, F., Chanal, J., Ratelle, C. F., Marsh, H. W., Larose, S., & Boivin, M. (2010). Intrinsic, identified, and controlled types of motivation for school subjects in young elementary school children. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 80(4), 711–735. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709910X499084>

Hassan, A. B., Lass, F. D., & Makinde, J. (2021). Cybercrime in Nigeria: Causes, effects, and the way out. *ARPJ Journal of Science and Technology*, 2(7), 626–631.

Hendery, S. (2024, March 14). HHS investigating “unprecedented” change in healthcare ransomware attack. *SC Media*. <https://www.scmagazine.com/news/hhs-investigating-unprecedented-change-healthcare-ransomware-attack>

Holt, T. J., Freilich, J. D., & Chermak, S. M. (2017). Exploring the subculture of ideologically motivated cyber-attackers. *Journal of Contemporary Criminal Justice*, 33(3), 212-233. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1043986217699100>

Hui, K. L., Kim, S. H., & Wang, Q. H. (2017). Cybercrime deterrence and international legislation: Evidence from distributed denial of service attacks. *MIS Quarterly*, 41(2), 497-524. <https://doi.org/10.25300/MISQ/2017/41.2.07>

Human Right Watch. (2020, April 2). Latin America: Cut prison crowding to fight COVID-19. *Human Right Watch*. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2020/04/02/latin-america-cut-prison-crowding-fight-covid-19>

Hutchings, A., & Chua, Y. (2017). Gendering cybercrime. In T. J. Holt (Ed.), *Cybercrime through an interdisciplinary lens* (pp. 167-188). Oxon: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315304140-10>

IBM Security Data Breach Report. (2024). Cost of a data breach report 2024. <https://www.ibm.com/reports/data-breach>

Ibrahim, S. (2016a). Social and contextual taxonomy of cybercrime: Socioeconomic theory of Nigerian cybercriminals. *International Journal of Law, Crime and Justice*, 47, 44-57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijlci.2016.06.001>

Ibrahim, S. (2016b, June). Causes of socioeconomic cybercrime in Nigeria. *Cybercrime and Computer Forensic*, 2(4), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijlci.2016.06.002>

Idehen, E. E., Ojewumi, A. K., & Olasupo, M. O. (2013). Influence of self-esteem and self-monitoring on attitudes towards internet fraud among undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. *African Research Review*, 7(2), 294-305. <https://doi.org/10.4314/afrrrev.v7i2.20>

Jegede, A. E., Elegbeleye, A. O., Olowookere, E. I., & Olorunyomi, B. R. (2016). Gendered alternative to cyber fraud participation: An assessment of technological driven crime in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Gender & Behaviour*, 14(3), 7672-7692. <https://doi.org/10.4314/gab.v14i3.2>

Jegede, A. E., Oyesomi, K. O., & Olorunyomi, B. R. (2016). Youth crime and the organized attributes of cyber fraud in the modern technological age: A thematic review. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 6(1), 153-164.

Karatgozianni, A. (2010). Blame it on the Russians: Tracking the portrayal of Russian hackers during cyber conflict incidents. *Digital Icons: Studies in Russian, Eurasian and Central European New Media*, 4, 127-150.

- Kaur, A. (2013). Maslow's need hierarchy theory: Applications and criticisms. *Global Journal of Management and Business Studies*, 3(10), 1061-1064. https://www.ripublication.com/gjmbsspl/gjmbssv3n10_06.pdf
- Kopecký, K. (2017). Online blackmail of Czech children focused on "sextortion" (Analysis of culprit and victim behaviors). *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(1), 11–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2016.04.014>
- Lavorgna, A., & Sergi, A. (2016). Serious, therefore organized? A critique of the emerging "cyber-organized crime" rhetoric in the United Kingdom. *International Journal of Cyber Criminology*, 10(2), 170-187. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.165899>
- Li, X. (2017). A review of motivations of illegal cyber activities. *Kriminologija & Socijalna Integracija: Časopis Za Kriminologiju, Penologiju i Poremećaje u Ponašanju*, 25(1), 110-126. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/3mhc7>
- Lynch, J. (2018, January 24). Police accuse two students, age 12, of cyberbullying in suicide. *CNN*. <https://edition.cnn.com/2018/01/23/us/florida-cyberstalking-charges-girl-suicide/index.html>
- Maslow, A. H. (1954). *Motivation and personality*. Harper and Row.
- McGuire, M., & Dowling, S. (2013). Cyber crime: A review of the evidence. Retrieved from https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/246749/horr75-summary.pdf
- Morgan, S. (2017). 2017 Cybercrime report. Available at <https://www.cybersecurity.com>. Accessed on: 12/07/2024.
- Mustard, D. (2010). How do labor markets affect crime? New evidence on an old puzzle. *IZA Discussion Paper*, 4856.
- Nicholson, J., & Higgins, G. E. (2017). Social structure social learning theory: Preventing crime and violence. In *Preventing crime and violence* (pp. 11-20). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-43845-7_2
- Ogunleye, O. Y., Ojedokun, A. U., & Aderinto, A. A. (2019). Pathways and motivations for cyber fraud involvement among female undergraduates of selected universities in South-West Nigeria. *International Journal of Cyber Criminology*, 13(2), 309-325. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3545054>
- Okeshola, F. B., & Adeta, A. K. (2013). The nature, causes, and consequences of cybercrime in tertiary institutions in Zaria-Kaduna State, Nigeria. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 3(9), 98-114.
- Olowu, D. (2009). Cyber-crimes and the boundaries of domestic legal responses: Case for an inclusionary framework for Africa. *Journal of Information, Law and Technology (JILT)*, 1, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1624289>
- Omodunbi, B. A., Odiase, P. O., Olaniyan, O. M., & Esan, A. O. (2016). Cybercrimes in Nigeria: Analysis, detection, and prevention. *FUOYE Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 1(1), 37-42. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/9whj7>
- Ogwezzy, M. C. (2012). Cybercrime and the proliferation of Yahoo addicts in Nigeria. *AGORA International Journal of Juridical Sciences*, 1, 86-102. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1641615>
- Oyebade, O. T., & Onyekwena, O. J. (2020). The impact of social media on youth involvement in cybercrime in Delta State: A qualitative analysis. *Journal of Digital Criminology*, 14(1), 32-50. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11417-020-09313-x>

- Reynolds, A. L. (2024). Profiling cybercriminals: Behavioral analysis and motivations behind cybercrime activities. *Cybersecurity Undergraduate Research Showcase*, 4. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.odu.edu/covacci-undergraduateresearch/2024spring/projects/4>
- Safko, L., & Brake, D. K. (2009). *The social media bible: Tactics, tools, and strategies for business success*. Hoboken, N.J.: John Wiley & Sons.
- Schmallegger, F., & Volk, R. (2018). *Canadian criminology today: Theories and applications* (6th ed.). Ontario: Pearson.
- Sharma, Adv. B. S. (2023, October 7). The psychology of cybercriminals: Unveiling motivations and driving factors. *LinkedIn*. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/psychology-cybercriminals-unveiling-motivations-driving-sharma>
- Suleman, I. (2016). Social and contextual taxonomy of cybercrime: Socioeconomic theory of Nigerian cybercriminals. *International Journal of Law, Crime and Justice*, 47(1), 44-57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijlci.2016.02.003>
- Taylor, P. A. (1999). *Hackers*. London: Routledge.
- The Deepwatch ATI 2024 Annual Threat Report. (2024). Retrieved from <https://www.deepwatch.com/2024-ati-threat-report/>
- Ulo, E., & Jike, T. V. (2022). Core family values as correlate of juvenile involvement in internet fraud in Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology Research*, 8(4), 1-13.
- Ulo, E. (2022). Socio-economic status and peer influence as correlate of juvenile involvement in internet fraud in Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications (IJSRP)*, 12(11). <https://doi.org/10.29322/IJSRP.12.11.2022.p13113>
- Ulo, E. (2023). Cyberspace anonymity: The root cause of internet fraud among Nigerian youths. *Ilorin Journal of Criminology and Security Studies*, 1(2), 1-18.
- Umejiaku, N. O., & Anyaegbu, M. I. (2016). Legal framework for the enforcement of cyber law and cyber ethics in Nigeria. *International Journal of Computer and Technology*, 15(10), 7130-7139. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1782378>
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2013). Comprehensive study on cybercrime. Retrieved from http://www.unodc.org/documents/organized_crime/UNODC_CCPCJ_EG.4_2013/CYBERCRIME_STUDY_210213.pdf
- Wolak, J., Finkelhor, D., Mitchell, K., & Ybarra, M. (2008). Online predators and their victims: Myths, realities, and implications for prevention and treatment. *American Psychologist*, 63(2), 111-128. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.63.2.111>
- Yazdanifard, R., Oyegoke, T., & Seyedi, A. (2011). Cyber-crimes: Challenges of the millennium age. In *Advances in Electrical Engineering and Electrical Machines* (pp. 527-534). Springer, Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-25905-0_68

